

Quadcopter

Authors:

Mohammed Arqam Mohiuddin, Dr. Abhay Kulkarni

* Mechanical Engineering, Jawaharlal Nehru Engineering College,

ABSTRACT: This paper presents the design and implementation of an aerial surveillance quadcopter for search and rescue applications. The aim of this research is to develop a real-time, compact and cost-effective drone that will be capable of search and rescue operations. The first phase of the paper considered modeling of the quadcopter while the second phase involved system implementation and simulation. The basic components used for the quadcopter design were Nirvaino Multi-rotor Flight Control Board, brushless motors, Electronic Speed Controllers (ESCs), SkyZone FPV Wireless Receiver, LiPoly Cell Battery, Mobius Camera, and 4mm Heat Shrink Tube. The design takes cognizance of the structure model, and hovering stability of the quadcopter. The frame of the quadcopter was made up of very light glass fiber to ensure stability while flying and also to reduce weight of the overall material. The entire design generated a compact and low cost surveillance quadcopter with weight of approximately 1.50kg; which can take photographs from environments with the aid of the onboard mounted camera. Live streaming was done with the help of laptop during flight.

Keywords: Quadcopter, Real-Time, Rotor-craft, Surveillance, Reconnaissance, Wireless Communication.

I Introduction

The need for flying vehicles was driven by advances in aeronautics, engineering, and embedded processing. Recent years, many researchers geared efforts towards flying compact robots or unmanned air vehicles (UAVs). Also defined as flying robots as aerial vehicles without the onboard presence of pilots. The need for compact UAVs is to forestall the menace posed by flying large size drones in dangerous environments. Today, there are different kinds of available UAV's model which are named according to the number of rotor it has. Quadcopter is one of such devices which are made of four rotors positioned equidistant to the center of mass of the device in order to generate lift and maneuverability.

Besides that, quadcopters move with the aid of electric motor, basically with four upwards rotors that facilitate any maneuvers within its flying area. It is designed in such a manner that it has a closed loop control to maintain a predefined trajectory, have automatic take-off and landing capabilities, and rotates above particular moving or stationary object of target. The dimensions of a quadcopter can vary

from the size of an insect to the size of an aerial vehicle depending on the type of application the UAV is meant for.

The first designed Quadcopter was utilized by the French engineer Etienne Oehmichen in 1924. Recently designed quadcopters are small in size, and deployed for applications such as in mining detection, aerial photography and surveillance. The configuration designs of quadcopters could be plus (+) or cross (x) configurations where the later handles the more payload.

Quadcopters unlike other aircrafts derive their thrust and movement from individual motor assembly or a set of revolving airfoils, and are controlled by its major axes (namely pitch, roll and yaw). The lift generators are run by high speed motor and balanced propellers which generate the thrust that lifts the craft above the ground level by pushing down the air flow. Quadcopters are controlled by varying the speed of its four rotors without any mechanical linkages required as obtainable in conventional helicopter.

This research is aimed at designing a real time wireless quadcopter that is appropriate for search and rescue operations. Ideally, the craft would be capable of autonomous flight and will be able to achieve a nominal flight altitude of about 7ft. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 highlights related works in order to bring the work in this paper into perspective; Section 3 analytically details the design considerations, and specifications, with the system block diagrams description; Section 4 presents the results obtained from testing of the completed work, finally, Section 5 concludes the paper.

II Review of Literatures

We described the model of a flying robot with gripper mechanism for surveillance purpose. The authors used aluminum frame to reduce the weight of the flying robot. The flight was able to lift more payloads due to the use of 1800KVA runner motor. However, the flying robot has the challenge of less flight time. Designed a miniature wireless quadcopter that has the capability of flying about and hovering like a helicopter with the aid of extra added motors. The software and hardware were carefully integrated to ensure a miniature technology but could not carry much payload. Proposed and designed the system and algorithms necessary to allow a quadcopter to autonomously locate and land on a station target. The quadcopter was able to hover in place but could not carry much payload. It was also meant for data collection or surveillance systems that only cope with moderately short battery life. In their design engaged an android operating system embedded in a smart phone to operate the quadcopter through graphical User Interface (GUI) and user's commands on the phone. The authors developed a small size UAV capable of taking photographs from environment though they did not consider issues of stability and carriage of higher payload other than the mounted camera. Developed a successful ISR quadcopter using cheap components. The author developed system platform that could be used as a low cost substitute to perform explosive detonation of army targets at high level of precision. The quadcopter however, could not resist much vibration and lacked stability.

Thus, amidst all the challenges listed above, this research is intended to design and implement a compact aerial surveillance quadcopter for search and rescue applications. The quadcopter would be capable of autonomous flight and will be able to achieve a nominal flight altitude of about 7ft. The total mass of the UAV will be below 2kg and the battery life will endure for at least 15 minutes. In all, the quadcopter will be capable of carrying moderate payload such as camera, and would be able to compensate for the external disturbances.

III Methodology

The concept of how quadcopters operate is fairly simple, but implementing each subsystem requires quite a bit of attention to detail in order for the aircraft to function properly. This section highlights the design methodology that was followed for the implementation of the quadcopter and details of how each subsystem works. The first phase of the project considered the design of the quadcopter while the second phase involved system implementation and simulation. The components used for the quadcopter design were duly tested and checked to ensure maximum safety and also to reduce cost.

1. Design Specification

The Specification for the design were listed in table 1 below and these determine the choice of suitable components.

Table 1: The specifications for the quadcopter design

Parameter	Value
Lifting thrust	7.50N.
Weight	Max. Component weight: 1.5kg
Battery	Type of cells – LiPoly cells (3S). Estimated flight time – 15mins.
Visibility	Suitable in clear weather only
Range of radio frequency coverage	1km

Frequency of video feed transmission	5.8GHz
Frequency of control signals	900MHz

2. Hardware Design

The following factors were put into consideration during design of the quadcopter.

2.1. The Quadcopter Body

The frame of the quadcopter was made of very light glass fiber. Many other materials such as aluminum and wood were considered. Aluminum was not used because of its inability to absorb vibration from the motors whereas wood could easily be destroyed by insects and weather conditions. The body of the quadcopter is divided into three parts: body frame, landing gear, and gimbal. The body frame enclosed all the needed components. The body frame was made slim with holes drilled to it to maintain stability while flying and to reduce the weight of the overall material. The width of the frame was 450mm and the height was 55mm. The gimbal was used to hold the camera in place and the landing gear was made to have a lower center of gravity for stability when landing the quadcopter.

2.2. Motors (Brushless) and Electronic Speed Controllers (ESCs)

Before choosing a motor for the design, the total weight which the UAV was meant to take was determined, and then the thrust required to lift the quadcopter was worked out. This was necessary because if the thrust provided by the motors were too little, the quadcopter will not respond well to control and will even have difficulties taking off, and if the thrust was too much, it might become too agile and hard to control. A rule of thumb required for thrust is given as:-

$$\text{Thrust} = (\text{weight} * 2) / 4 \text{ (For 2:1 thrust / weight ratio)}$$

Where: weight = estimated weight of loaded vehicle which is obtained by adding the individual weights of all motors, propellers, ESCs, camera etc. The list of components with their respective weight is tabulated in Table 2 below:

Table 2: List of the components with their respective weight estimates

S/N	Components	Estimated weight per unit	Number of units	Total Weight
1.	Brushless Motors	70g	4	280g
2.	Propellers	15g	4	60g
3.	Mobius Camera	39g	1	39g
4.	LiPoly Cell Battery	278g	1	278g
5.	Frame	270g	1	270g
6.	TURNIGY K-Force 30A Brushless ESC	25g	4	100g
7.	Power distribution Board	55g	1	55g
8.	4mm Heat Shrink Tube	10g	2	20
9.	SkyZone FPV Wireless Receiver	25g	1	25
			TOTAL	1127g

2.3. On-Board Power Supply

The entire system is battery powered. The battery is a LiPoly 3S pack which has an output voltage of 11.1V and a capacity of 3000mAh. It is connected to the ESCs through the PCB in the frame. The electronic speed controllers (ESCs) which feature a built in battery eliminator circuit (BEC) of output 5V/2A then supplies the 5V which is required to power the microcontroller. The battery is also used to power the camera and the Skyzone transmitter.

In choosing a battery, it is usually ideal that the amperage of the battery pack should exceed that of the motor. This ensures that even when the motor is running at 100%, the battery will not hold it

back. Therefore to have optimum power/weight combination, a battery pack just above the motors amperage should be chosen. The motor's amperage is calculated as follows: maximum power of motor = 270W, battery voltage (3s Li-Po) = $3 \times 3.7V = 11.1V$ (Where 3.7V is the nominal voltage for each cell), maximum per motor amperage = 18A

2.4. Image/Video capture device:

The image capture device is the FPV camera (Mobius Wide Angle C Lens). It has a resolution of 5mega pixels and is capable of capturing HD videos. It is connected to a 5.8GHz transmitter which transmits wirelessly to a 5.8GHz receiver, and also connected to a computer for live feeds. The image/video capture device (camera) is mounted on the tabs at the bottom plate of the main frame. The mounting tab holds the camera in place and the wide view angle of the camera eliminates the need for a servo motor. This ultimately reduced the weight and power requirement of the entire system.

2.5. GPS Navigation:

The GPS navigation enables the quadcopter to independently make its way to a given target location.

2.6. Image/Video capture device:

The microcontroller board's firmware monitors measurement devices (gyroscope, magnetometer and accelerometer) that make up the Inertial Measurement Units (IMU) to get the current state of the quadcopter, along with the operator's input (desired state) and sends signals to the ESCs attached to each of the motors. The ESCs use these inputs received from the microcontroller to deliver the power required the power required to control the speed of the motors. Each ESC has a processor, firmware and other electronics that manage this task by rapidly switching the power to the motor on and off. Each motor either in a clockwise or anticlockwise direction. Figure 1 below is used to illustrate the quadcopter direction based on the variation of the speed of the motors.

Fig.1: Basic Motion of Quadcopters

2.7. Communication System:

The laptop served as the main input for control signals and the signals were transmitted to the microcontroller and vice versa through the use of the Skyzone RF modules that have been configured to communicate with one another. This is displayed in figure 2 below:

Fig.2: Transceiver

A manual transceiver was also used to override the Autopilot mode of the quadcopter. Turnigy Transceiver shown in figure 3 was used. The transceiver system has a nine channel Transmitter and an eight channel receiver. It uses pulse position modulation encoding scheme at the transmitter and pulse code modulation encoding scheme at the receiver.

Fig. 3: Turnigy Transmitter

2.7.The Microcontroller:

Nirvaino Multi-rotor Flight Control Board is the primary flight controller at the heart of the Nirvaino Arduino Pro Mini's Atmel Mega368 8-bit AVR RISC-based microcontroller with 64k of memory. The block diagram in figure 4 below shows the input/output relationship of all other components to the microcontroller.

Fig.4: Block diagram showing the input/output relationship of other components to the flight controller

IV SIMULATION RESULTS

The data used for the quadcopter simulation was based on our system design as shown in Table 4 below. The individual parameters of the components that make up our quadcopter were carefully calculated. Some parameters such as Torque, Thrust and time constants were carefully estimated from already measured data of a similar system. This estimation was due to the unavailability of a test bench which was required to carefully monitor and measure these parameters.

Table 4: Quadcopter Modeling Parameters

Parameters	Value
Gross mass, m	1.5kg
Time constant	0.076s
Minimum throttle	5%
Thrust coefficient, c_q	$2.925e-9$ NM/RPM ²

%throttle to RPM conversion constant, cr	80.584RPM/%
Mass Moment of inertial across the x-axis, Jx	0.0085136kgm ²
Mass Moment of inertial across the y-axis, Jy	0.0085136kgm ²
Mass Moment of inertial across the z-axis, Jz	0.016334kgm ²

The PID Controller gains of the various controllers were carefully tuned and appropriate gains were chosen based on the simulation results obtained. The simulation was run for 300 seconds and graph were generated.

V CONCLUSION

This paper designed and simulated a real time aerial quadcopter for search and rescue operations. A small size, less weight, intelligent, surveillance and reconnaissance quadcopter which can take the photographs from environment was realized through the aid of the onboard mounted camera while live streaming was done on the laptop during flight. After implementing and testing the quadcopter, the quadcopter met its weight requirement. Its approximate weight was 1.50kg. The motors and ESCs were successfully calibrated; the requirement of best minimized size was met; and communication from the ground control station to the quadcopter was achieved.

5.1 Recommendations

The motors should be firmly fastened to the arms of the chassis in order to reduce vibrations. When fixing the propellers to the motors a washer should be added to have a firm grip to prevent it from snipping off. Spare parts should be available in case of faults or need for replacement. The use of brushless motors will help not only in reducing vibrations but also consume lesser power. Also, use light materials for constructing the chassis to reduce the weight but also strong to withstand vibration from motors and propellers. The frame should be made such that there is enough clearance between each motor to make enough room for the rotation of the propellers. The frame should be aerodynamic. Assembling of the entire system should be done such that the center of mass is concentrated at the center of the system.

5.2 Research for Further Study

Power Improvement: Majority of the weight / mass of the system is due to the battery. This affects the total torque/ lifting power of the quadcopter. Also, batteries have very limited flight time. Research on a better alternative of power such as fuel cells should therefore be carried out.

REFERENCES

1. Bouabdallah, S., Noth, A., & Siegwart, R. (2004). PID vs LQ control techniques applied to an indoor micro quadrotor. Proceedings of the 2004 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), 2451-2456.
2. Mellinger, D., & Kumar, V. (2011). Minimum snap trajectory generation and control for quadrotors. Proceedings of the 2011 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA), 2520-2525.
3. Mahony, R., Kumar, V., & Corke, P. (2012). Multirotor aerial vehicles: Modeling, estimation, and control of quadrotor. IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine, 19(3), 20-32.
4. Fraundorfer, F., & Scaramuzza, D. (2012). Visual odometry: Part II - Matching, robustness, and applications. IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine, 19(2), 78-90.
5. Zhang, W., & Dissanayake, G. (2014). Visual-inertial sensor fusion: Localization, mapping, and sensor-to-sensor self-calibration. IEEE Transactions on Robotics, 30(2), 314-329.
6. Scaramuzza, D., & Fraundorfer, F. (2011). Visual odometry: Part I - The first 30 years and fundamentals. IEEE Robotics & Automation Magazine, 18(4), 80-92.
7. Bouabdallah, S., & Siegwart, R. (2005). Backstepping and sliding-mode techniques applied to an indoor micro quadrotor. Proceedings of the 2005 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA), 2247-2252.
8. Ryll, M., & Stolkin, R. (2017). Active vision-based mapping and exploration for visual servoing of a quadrotor UAV. IEEE Transactions on Robotics, 33(6), 1481-1496.